

Reservoirs of Antimicrobial Resistance: A Comparative Study of Hospital and Community Settings in Calabar, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Antimicrobial resistance represents a critical global health challenge requiring comprehensive surveillance across healthcare and community environments to understand transmission dynamics and resistance patterns. **Objective:** This study aimed to assess the level of antimicrobial resistance in clinical and environmental Gram-negative bacterial isolates in Calabar, Nigeria and determine their multiple antibiotic resistance indices. **Methodology:** This comparative study examined 105 clinical samples from two hospitals. Additionally, 210 environmental samples from hospital sources (door handles, sinks, dump sites) and community sources (sachet water, poultry litter, processed meat), with 35 samples per category, were collected. These were analyzed using standard bacteriological procedures, Vitek identification systems and modified Kirby-Bauer antimicrobial susceptibility testing protocols with ten antibiotics from six classes of antibiotics. **Results:** Twenty-eight (13.3%) gram-negative isolates were recovered from environmental sources, predominantly from poultry litter 14(50%) and dump sites 10(35%), with significant association between sample sources and organism recovery ($\chi^2=14.412$, $p=0.001$). Forty (38.1%) gram-negative isolates were recovered from clinical samples. *Escherichia coli* emerged as the predominant isolate in both environmental (30%) and clinical (23.3%) samples. Environmental isolates demonstrated variable resistance patterns with Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index (MARI) values range of 0.1-0.5 (mean 0.3 ± 0.05), while clinical isolates showed higher resistance levels with MARI of 0.2-0.8 (mean 0.4 ± 0.06). Multidrug resistance was prevalent among clinical isolates, with six bacterial species exhibiting 100% MDR rates. Cefuroxime was the most resisted antibiotic with highest resistance rates in both environmental (60%) and clinical (90%) isolates, while meropenem demonstrated superior efficacy with minimal resistance. **Conclusion:** The study revealed significant antimicrobial resistance reservoirs in both hospital and community settings, with clinical isolates demonstrating higher resistance levels than environmental counterparts. These findings emphasize the urgent need for comprehensive surveillance and targeted intervention strategies.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, Multidrug resistance, Environmental surveillance, Clinical isolates, Gram-negative bacteria, Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index (MARI)

INTRODUCTION

Antimicrobial resistance represents one of the most pressing global health challenges of our time, with the World Health Organization African region experiencing a disproportionate burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance, contributing to substantial morbidity and mortality across diverse healthcare systems [1]. This phenomenon has evolved beyond isolated clinical occurrences to become a complex ecological issue that transcends traditional boundaries between healthcare facilities and broader community environments [2].

The conceptual framework of antimicrobial resistance reservoirs has gained considerable attention in recent years, fundamentally challenging our understanding of how resistant pathogens persist, proliferate, and disseminate across different environmental niches [3]. These reservoirs function as dynamic ecosystems where resistant organisms can establish themselves, undergo genetic exchange, and subsequently spread to susceptible populations through various transmission pathways. Healthcare institutions have been identified as particularly significant drivers and amplifiers of antimicrobial resistance, creating conditions that favor the selection and maintenance of resistant bacterial populations [4].

The traditional perspective that antimicrobial-resistant infections originate primarily from healthcare settings have been increasingly questioned, with mounting evidence suggesting that community environments may serve as equally important sources of resistance emergence and persistence [2]. Recent investigations across African contexts have revealed substantial prevalence of

antibiotic resistance in commensal bacteria from healthy community members, indicating widespread circulation of resistant organisms outside clinical environments [5]. Similarly, comparative analyses between hospitalized patients and community residents have demonstrated complex patterns of colonization with resistant organisms that vary significantly across different geographical and socioeconomic contexts [6].

Within the African healthcare landscape, antimicrobial resistance presents unique challenges characterized by limited surveillance infrastructure, variable access to diagnostic capabilities, and diverse antimicrobial usage patterns that may influence resistance development differently across hospital and community settings [7]. Nigeria, as the most populous African nation, represents a critical focal point for understanding these dynamics, particularly given the complex interplay between formal healthcare delivery systems and community-based health practices that characterize the region's epidemiological environment [8].

Environmental factors further complicate the resistance landscape, with biofilms and built environments serving as persistent reservoirs that can harbor resistant organisms for extended periods [9]. Hospital premises themselves may function as reservoirs, with resistant organisms establishing themselves within institutional infrastructure and potentially contributing to patient infections [10]. Recent evidence suggests that newly constructed hospital environments can rapidly develop established populations of antibiotic-resistant organisms that subsequently relate to patient bloodstream

infections, highlighting the dynamic nature of institutional resistance ecology [11].

The complexity of resistance reservoirs extends beyond human clinical isolates to encompass broader ecological networks, including animal and environmental sources that contribute to the overall resistance burden through interconnected pathways [12]. This One Health perspective emphasizes the need for comprehensive surveillance approaches that can capture resistance patterns across multiple ecological compartments and identify the relative contributions of different reservoir types to overall resistance dynamics [12].

Despite growing recognition of the importance of comparative reservoir studies, significant knowledge gaps persist regarding the specific characteristics of antimicrobial resistance patterns between hospital and community settings within Nigerian contexts. This study aimed to conduct a comparative analysis of antimicrobial resistance reservoirs between hospital and community settings in Calabar, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to characterize the prevalence and patterns of antimicrobial resistance across these distinct environments, identify key bacterial species serving as resistance reservoirs, and evaluate the relationship between resistance profiles observed in clinical and community contexts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and setting

The study was conducted in Calabar, the capital and commercial hub of Cross River State, located in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. It was a cross-sectional study carried out at the General Hospital, Calabar, and the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital (UCTH) from May - November 2025

with support from Tetfund. The UCTH, a 450-bed facility and the largest in Cross River State, also serves as a major tertiary referral center for the State.

Sample collection and processing

A total of 105 clinical specimens including urine, wound swab, ear swab, high vaginal swab, stool, cerebrospinal fluid, and sputum were aseptically collected and processed at the diagnostic microbiological laboratories of two major government hospitals (Teaching and General Hospitals) in Calabar, with socio-demographic and clinical data obtained from patient records. Also, six groups of environmental samples were collected, three from hospital environments (door handles, hospital sinks, and waste dump sites) and three from community settings (sachet water, poultry litters, and processed meat pie). All clinical isolates were preserved on slants, sub-cultured individually, and gram-positive organisms were excluded from the study to focus specifically on gram-negative bacterial resistance patterns across both clinical and environmental sources.

Bacterial identification

All samples were subjected to culture on Nutrient Agar (Oxoid, UK). The Gram staining procedure was carried out to differentiate Gram-negative and Gram-positive organisms. Bacteria appearing pale to dark red (bacilli) were identified as gram-negative and included in the study, while those appearing dark purple were classified as gram-positive and excluded, as this investigation focused specifically on gram-negative organisms.

Vitek 2 Compact gram-negative identification system

Forty Gram-negative bacterial isolates (30 clinical and 10 environmental) from the study

were identified using the Vitek 2 Compact automated microbiology system (BioMérieux, France), which utilizes biochemical substances contained in specialized gram-negative identification strips. Fresh isolates were sub-cultured on nutrient agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, after which two colonies were emulsified in either 5.0 ml of sterile normal saline (0.85%) to prepare standardized inocula for automated identification using the Vitek 2 system.

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing

Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed using the modified Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method. Test isolates were suspended in 7 ml nutrient broth and adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standard turbidity as described by Chesbrough (2000). The standardized bacterial suspension was uniformly swabbed onto 4 mm thick Mueller-Hinton agar plates (Nissan Tokyo, Japan) using sterile swab sticks, with duplicate plates prepared for each isolate and allowed to dry for five minutes before antibiotic disc placement.

Antibiotic panel selection

Ten commercially prepared antibiotic discs (Mask Diagnostic GmbH, Germany) representing six major antimicrobial classes

were employed: carbapenem (meropenem 30µg), cephalosporins (cefixime 5µg, ceftazidime 30µg, ceftriaxone 30µg, cefuroxime 30µg), penicillin/beta-lactamase inhibitor combinations (amoxicillin-clavulanate 20/10µg, piperacillin/tazobactam 100/10µg), quinolones/ fluoroquinolones (levofloxacin 5µg, ciprofloxacin 5µg), and aminoglycosides (amikacin 30µg).

Disc placement and incubation protocol

Antibiotic discs were aseptically placed on inoculated plates using sterile forceps, with five discs per plate maintaining a minimum 3 cm separation distance between discs. All plates were incubated inverted at 37°C for 24 hours before examination. Following incubation, inhibition zone diameters were measured in millimeters using a ruler from the underside of plates. Measured zone diameters were interpreted according to Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) 2022 guidelines to determine antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of the test isolates.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Cross River State Health Research Ethics Committee, Ministry of Health Headquarters, Calabar (Reference Number: CRS/MH/HREC/2021/VOL.VI/115).

RESULTS

Table 1: Gram negative bacteria isolated from the environment

Environment	Sample Type	Number examined (n)	Gram negative isolates		
			N	%	
Within hospital	Door handle	35	0	0.0	$\chi^2=14.412$ p=0.001
	Hospital sinks	35	3	10.7	
	Dump site	35	10	35.7	
Community	Sachet water	35	0	0.0	
	Poultry litters	35	14	50.0	
	Processed meat	35	1	3.6	
	Total	210	28	13.3	

Table 2: Sources and distribution of clinical samples

Source of clinical isolates	No. of samples collected	University of Calabar Teaching Hospital Calabar	General Hospital Calabar	Statistics
Stool	11 (10.4%)	6 (8.6%)	5 (14.3%)	$\chi^2 = 11.031$ p=0.075
Wound swab	14 (13.3%)	14 (20.0)	0 (0.0%)	
Urine	32 (30.5%)	24 (34.3%)	8 (22.8%)	
Sputum	7 (6.7%)	4 (5.7%)	3 (8.6%)	
Blood culture	10 (9.5%)	7 (10.0%)	3 (8.6%)	
Genital swab	26 (24.8%)	14 (20.0%)	12 (34.3%)	
Ear swab	5 (4.8%)	1 (1.4%)	4 (11.4%)	
Total	105 (100%)	70 (100%)	35 (100%)	

Figure 1: Distribution of environmental Gram-negative bacterial isolates identified with Vitek (Kolmogorov-Smirnov; K-S = 0.421; p = 0.001)

Figure 2: Distribution of clinical Gram-negative bacterial isolates identified with Vitek (Kolmogorov-Smirnov; K-S = 0.278; p = 0.001)

Table 3: Antibiotics resistance pattern of environmental Gram-negative isolates

Environmental isolates	No. examined	MEM	CFM	AUG	CAZ	TZP	CRO	CXM	LEV	CIP	AK	
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	$\chi^2 = 30.099;$ $p=0.001$
<i>E. coli</i>	3	0	1	2	1	1	0	2	1	0	0	
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	
<i>A. ursingii</i>	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	
<i>Pantoea spp.</i>	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	
<i>C. pauculus</i>	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	
<i>A. faecalis</i>	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	
Total	10	0	5	5	4	4	1	7	3	1	1	
%	100	0.0	50.0	50.0	40.0	40.0	10.0	70.0	30.0	10.0	10.0	

Key: 1 = Resistant 0 = Sensitive

KEY: MEM = meropenem, CFM = Cefixime, AUG = Augmentin, CAZ = Ceftazidime; TZP = Piperacillin/Tazobactam, CRO = Ceftriaxone, CXM = Cefuroxime, LEV = Levofloxacin, CIP = Ciprofloxacin, AK = Amikacin

Table 4: Antibiotics resistance pattern of clinical Gram-negative isolates

Clinical Organisms	No. examined											
		MEM	CFM	AUG	CAZ	TZP	CRO	CXM	LEV	CIP	AK	
<i>E. cloacae</i>	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	$\chi^2 = 26.485;$ $p=0.001$
<i>Pantoea</i> spp.	2	0	2	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	
<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	
<i>P. florescence</i>	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	5	0	3	3	4	3	5	5	3	2	2	
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	4	1	3	4	3	2	1	4	0	1	1	
<i>E. coli</i>	7	1	4	6	6	4	2	7	3	5	4	
<i>P. vulgaris</i>	2	0	1	2	1	0	2	2	1	0	0	
<i>A. baumannii</i>	4	0	3	4	4	1	2	4	4	3	2	
<i>P. putida</i>	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	
Unidentified org.	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Total (n)	30	4	20	24	21	12	15	27	12	11	10	
%	100	13.3	66.7	80.0	70.0	40.0	50.0	90.0	40.0	36.7	33.3	

Key: 1 = Resistant 0 = Sensitive

KEY: MEM = meropenem, CFM = Cefixime, AUG = Augmentin, CAZ = Ceftazidime; TZP = Piperacillin/Tazobactam, CRO = Ceftriaxone, CXM = Cefuroxime, LEV = Levofloxacin, CIP = Ciprofloxacin, AK = Amikacin

Table 5: Prevalence of multidrug resistance (MDR) among the environmental bacterial isolates

Bacterial isolates	Class of antibiotics N (%)						MDR (%)	
	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	MDR (%)		
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (n=2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	$\chi^2 = 43.028$ $p=0.001$
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (n=3)	1(33.3)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1(33.3)	1(33.3)	
<i>Proteus</i> spp. (n = 1)	0 (0)	1(100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1(100)	
<i>Acinetobacter ursingii</i> (n=1)	0 (0)	1(100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1(100)	
<i>Pantoea</i> spp. (n=1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	
<i>Cupriavidus pauculus</i> (n=1)	1 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (100)	
<i>Alcaligenes faecalis</i> (n=1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	

Classes of antibiotics used are carbapenem (meropenem), cephalosporins (cefixime, ceftazidime, ceftriaxone and cefuroxime) penicillin (Augmentin) penicillin /beta-lactamase inhibitor (piperacillin/ tazobactams) quinolone (levofloxacin), fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin) and aminoglycoside (amikacin)

Table 6: Prevalence of multidrug resistance (MDR) among clinical bacterial isolates

Bacterial isolates (n = 28)	Class of antibiotics N (%)					MDR (%)	
	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7		
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> (n=1)	1(100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (100)	$\chi^2 = 16.113$ p=0.001
<i>Pantoea</i> spp. (n=2)	0 (0)	1(50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1(50)	
<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i> (n=1)	1 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (100)	
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> (n=1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (n=5)	0 (0)	1(20)	2(40)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3 (60)	
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i> (n = 4)	3 (37)	1 (25)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (100)	
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (n=7)	3 (43)	0 (0)	3(43)	1(14)	0 (0)	7 (100)	
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i> (n=2)	1(50)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1(50)	
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (n=4)	0 (0)	2(50)	0 (0)	2(50)	0 (0)	4(100)	
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> (n=1)	1(100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1(100)	

Classes of antibiotics used are carbapenem (meropenem), cephalosporins (cefixime, ceftazidime, ceftriaxone and cefuroxime) penicillin (Augmentin) penicillin /beta-lactamase inhibitor (piperacillin/ tazobactams) quinolone (levofloxacin), fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin) and aminoglycoside (amikacin)

Table 7: Multiple Antibiotic resistance index of environmental Gram-negative bacterial isolates

Environmental Bacterial Isolates (n=10)	No. of antibiotic tested	No. of antibiotic resisted by isolate	No. (%) of isolates	MAR Index	Statistics
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (n=3)	10	1	1(33.3)	0.1	$\bar{X} = 0.3 \pm \text{SEM}$ 0.05
		2	1(33.3)	0.2	
		5	1(33.3)	0.5	
<i>Proteus</i> spp. (n = 1)	10	3	1(100)	0.3	
<i>Acinetobacter ursingii</i> (n=1)	10	5	1(100)	0.5	
<i>Cupriavidus pauculus</i> (n=1)	10	4	1(100)	0.4	
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (n=2)	10	1	1(50)	0.1	
		2	1(50)	0.2	
<i>Pantoea</i> spp. (n=1)	10	5	1(100)	0.5	
<i>Alkaligenes faecalis</i> (n=1)	10	3	1(100)	0.3	

The mean MARI was significantly different for clinical and environmental isolates using Mann-Whitney U = 6.000; p=0.003.

Table 8: Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index of the clinical bacterial isolates

Clinical Bacterial isolates (n=28)	No. of antibiotic tested	No. of antibiotic resisted by isolate	No. (%) of isolates	MAR Index	Statistics
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (n=7)	10	4	2(28.5)	0.4	$\bar{X} = 0.4 \pm \text{SEM}$ 0.06
		5	2(28.5)	0.5	
		6	1(14.3)	0.6	
		7	2(28.5)	0.7	
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (n=4)	10	5	1(25.0)	0.5	
		7	3(75.0)	0.7	
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> (n=1)	10	6	1(100)	0.6	
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (n=5)	10	5	2(40)	0.5	
		6	1(20)	0.6	
		8	2(40)	0.8	
<i>Proteus Mirabilis</i> (n = 4)	10	4	1(25)	0.4	
		5	2(50)	0.5	
		6	1(25)	0.6	
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i> (n=2)	10	5	2(100)	0.5	
<i>Pantoea</i> spp. (n=2)	10	2	1(50)	0.2	
		5	1(50)	0.5	
<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i> (n=1)	10	5	1(100)	0.5	
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i> (n=1)	10	5	1(100)	0.5	
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> (n=1)	10	5	1(100)	0.5	

DISCUSSION

The recovery of gram-negative bacteria from various environmental sources revealed distinct patterns of contamination across hospital and community settings (Table 1). The absence of bacterial isolates from door handles and sachet water suggests these particular sources may be either less prone to contamination or subject to different environmental pressures that limit bacterial survival such as disinfection. Hospital sinks demonstrated a relatively low recovery rate of 11% compared to dump sites at 35%,

indicating that while hospital environments may maintain better infection control protocols, they are not entirely free from resistant organisms [13]. The significantly higher isolation rates from poultry litter (50%) underscores the role of agricultural settings as potential reservoirs of antimicrobial resistance, consistent with concerns about antibiotic use in livestock production systems (Table 1) [14].

The distribution of clinical isolates between the two participating hospitals demonstrates a

balanced sample representation, with urine samples constituting the largest proportion at 30.5% of total samples. This finding aligns with global surveillance data showing urinary tract infections as a leading source of clinical bacterial isolates in hospital settings [15]. The predominance of urine samples reflects both the common occurrence of urinary tract infections in hospitalized patients and the routine nature of urine culture in clinical diagnostics. The lack of significant association between sample distribution and hospital source ($p = 0.087$) suggests that bacterial infection patterns are relatively consistent across similar healthcare facilities, supporting the generalizability of resistance patterns observed in this study (Table 2) [16].

Bacterial species identification and distribution patterns

The Vitek system identification of environmental isolates revealed *Escherichia coli* as the most prevalent organism at 30%, followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* at 20%. This distribution pattern reflects the environmental persistence and adaptability of these enterobacterial species, which are well-established as successful colonizers of diverse ecological niches [17]. The presence of less common organisms such as *Cupriavidus pauculus* and *Alcaligenes faecalis* in environmental samples indicates the diverse bacterial community that exists outside clinical settings, potentially serving as a reservoir for horizontal gene transfer events that can contribute to resistance dissemination (Figure 1) [18].

Clinical isolates demonstrated a similar predominance of *E. coli* (23.3%) and *K. pneumoniae* (16.7%), consistent with their established roles as leading causes of healthcare-associated infections globally [19]. The presence of *Acinetobacter baumannii*

(13.3%) and *Proteus mirabilis* (13.3%) reflects their importance as nosocomial pathogens, particularly in intensive care settings where these organisms are associated with ventilator-associated pneumonia and catheter-related infections [20]. The identification of *Pseudomonas* species in clinical samples highlights their particular relevance in hospital environments, where their intrinsic resistance mechanisms and biofilm-forming capabilities make them formidable healthcare-associated pathogens [21].

Antibiotic resistance patterns in environmental and clinical isolates

The antibiotic resistance profile of environmental isolates demonstrates concerning patterns, with cefuroxime being the highest resisted with rate at 60% among tested organisms. This finding is particularly significant given that cefuroxime is a second-generation cephalosporin commonly used in empirical therapy, suggesting that environmental bacteria may serve as a reservoir for clinically relevant resistance mechanisms [22]. The complete absence of meropenem resistance in environmental isolates provides some reassurance regarding the preservation of carbapenem effectiveness, though continued surveillance is essential given the critical role of these antibiotics in treating multidrug-resistant infections (Table 3) [23].

The observation that *E. coli* isolates from environmental sources showed resistance to six different antibiotics highlights the concerning capacity of this species to acquire and maintain multiple resistance determinants. This finding is consistent with global reports of *E. coli* as a key indicator organism for monitoring the spread of antimicrobial resistance in environmental

settings [24]. The extensive antibiotic use across various sectors in Nigeria and ineffective antimicrobial stewardship programmes may contribute to the selection pressure driving these resistance patterns in environmental bacteria (Table 3).

The resistance patterns observed in clinical isolates present a more alarming picture, with *E. coli* demonstrating pan-resistance to all tested antibiotics and *K. pneumoniae*, *P. mirabilis*, and *A. baumannii* each showing resistance to 9 of 10 tested antibiotics. These findings reflect the intense selective pressure present in hospital environments, where repeated antibiotic exposure drives the evolution and selection of highly resistant bacterial populations [25]. The relatively low resistance rate to meropenem (13.3%) among clinical isolates reinforces its position as a last-resort antibiotic, though the presence of any carbapenem resistance is concerning given the limited therapeutic alternatives available (Table 4) [26].

The 90% resistance rate to cefuroxime among clinical isolates represents a critical limitation for empirical therapy protocols in the study hospitals (Table 4). This finding necessitates urgent revision of antibiotic prescribing guidelines and highlights the importance of antimicrobial stewardship programs in Nigerian healthcare facilities [27]. The Federal Government of Nigeria has launched the Second National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR 2.0) as part of efforts to address these challenges systematically.

Multidrug resistance prevalence and patterns

The analysis of multidrug resistance patterns among environmental isolates reveals a mixed picture, with some organisms such as *K. pneumoniae*, *Pantoea* spp., and *A. faecalis*

showing no multidrug resistance, while others like *Proteus* spp. and *A. ursingii* demonstrated significant MDR patterns. This heterogeneity suggests that environmental selection pressures vary considerably depending on the specific ecological niche and exposure to antimicrobial compounds [28]. The significant association between multidrug resistance and organism type ($p = 0.001$) indicates that certain bacterial species are more prone to acquiring and maintaining multiple resistance mechanisms (Table 5).

Clinical isolates demonstrated alarming MDR rates, with six bacterial species showing 100% MDR prevalence. This finding reflects the intense selective pressure within hospital environments and highlights the urgent need for enhanced infection prevention and control measures [29]. The 60% MDR rate observed in *K. pneumoniae* clinical isolates is consistent with global surveillance data showing this organism as a leading cause of healthcare-associated infections with extensive drug resistance profiles (Table 6) [30]. These findings underscore the critical importance of rapid diagnostic testing and targeted therapy to preserve the effectiveness of remaining active antibiotics.

Multiple antibiotic resistance index analysis

The Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index (MARI) analysis provides quantitative insight into the extent of resistance across different bacterial populations. Environmental isolates showed MARI values ranging from 0.1 to 0.5, with a mean of 0.3 ± 0.05 , indicating moderate levels of multidrug resistance in the community environment (Table 7) [31]. The variability observed within species, particularly *E. coli*, suggests that resistance acquisition is an ongoing process with considerable strain-to-strain variation even

within the same species and environmental setting [32, 33].

Clinical isolates demonstrated significantly higher MARI values (mean 0.4 ± 0.06), with some organisms reaching MARI values as high as 0.8 (Table 8). This statistically significant difference ($p=0.003$) between environmental and clinical isolates agrees that hospital environments represent amplification points for antimicrobial resistance [32]. The particularly high MARI values observed in *K. pneumoniae* (up to 0.8) and *E. coli* (up to 0.7) clinical isolates reflect their successful adaptation to the antibiotic-rich hospital environment and their role as priority pathogens for antimicrobial resistance surveillance [34-36]. The study findings align with broader regional challenges in addressing antimicrobial resistance in Africa, where the infection worsens, resistance increases, and another patient is added to the silent pandemic of antimicrobial resistance. The global campaign raises awareness and understanding of AMR, while promoting best practices, with the 2024 theme emphasizing the imperative of urgent, coordinated action against the threat.

CONCLUSION

The findings from this study demonstrates the complex connections between hospital and community reservoirs of antimicrobial resistance. The prevalence of clinical Gram-negative bacteria in the study was 38.1% and 13.3% for environmental isolates. Poultry litter and dump sites yielded the most Gram-negative isolates, 14(50%) and 10(35%) respectively. *Escherichia coli* emerged as the predominant isolate in both environmental (30%) and clinical (23.3%) samples with MARI of 0.7 followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* with MARI of 0.8. Multidrug resistance was prevalent among clinical isolates, with six

bacterial species exhibiting 100% MDR rates. The detection of resistant organisms in environmental settings such as poultry litter and dump sites show that resistance development is not confined to clinical settings but represents a broader ecological phenomenon. This supports the implementation of One Health approach that recognizes the interconnected nature of human, animal, and environmental health in addressing antimicrobial resistance challenges. The presence of clinically relevant resistant bacteria in community environments raises concerns about the potential for horizontal gene transfer and the establishment of resistance reservoirs that can subsequently seed hospital environments with pre-existing resistant organisms. This two-way exchange between hospital and community settings necessitates coordinated surveillance and intervention strategies that extend beyond traditional healthcare boundaries.

Limitations

This study focused on one specific geographical region, implying that the findings may not apply to other areas with different environmental and healthcare conditions. Also, the study design only captured resistance patterns at one point in time. Future research may need to use longer-term monitoring approaches to better understand how resistance develops and spreads between different environments over time.

Recommendations

Future studies should include molecular analysis of resistance mechanisms to understand the genetic basis of these patterns and track specific resistance genes across different settings. Using whole genome sequencing could reveal how environmental

and clinical bacterial isolates are related, potentially showing transmission pathways and helping design targeted interventions. Additionally, expanding sampling to include different geographical regions and environmental areas would improve our understanding of antimicrobial resistance patterns across sub-Saharan Africa more broadly.

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